

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN LEADERSHIP COACHING, MOTIVATION, AND EMPLOYEE INNOVATION, A STUDY RELATED TO INDIAN KPOS

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ABSTRACT

With globalization entering a new stage, innovation has become the primary force behind development. The task of motivating employees to engage in innovative behavior has become a hot topic in the field of organization research. Coached leadership is a style of leadership in the field of organizational behavior that can improve employees' minds. A study based on the Self-Determination Theory shows that coaching leadership can effectively promote innovative behavior and promote motivation. The study was conducted by conducting a survey of 120 respondents from 5 leading KPO organizations in Pune City. The results of the study indicate that Level of leadership coaching and Work motivation have significant positive correlations with employee innovation.

Keywords: Leadership Coaching, motivation, innovation, Indian KPOs

1. Introduction

As India's economic development enters a new phase, enterprises must adapt to the changing environment. The goal of stable development is innovation, and employee innovation is a key component of the company's competitiveness. In the research field, a hot topic has been how to motivate employees' innovative behavior. The leadership from 5 leading KPO organizations in Pune City, style, as a form of leadership born in a dynamic organization, has a unique advantage in improving employee mental models and inspiring innovation (Wang et.al. 2016). Innovation research, however, tends to focus on mature leadership styles, like transformational leadership and empowerment leadership. Few studies have explored how coaching leadership influences employee innovation behavior. Motivation, however, drives people to behave in certain ways. A leader's attitude and behavior influence employees' needs, as well as their recognition of their positions and organizations, according to the self-determination theory. We should explore how work motivation influences coaching leadership and innovation. As such, this study aims to analyze the intrinsic influence mechanism of coaching leadership on employee innovation behavior based on the SDT so as to provide advice on how to enhance innovation and competitiveness within organizations.

2. Literature Review

In recent years, coaching leadership has received much attention. The book suggests that leaders use coaching skills to help employees identify deeper needs, set goals, and improve their performance. Coaches were introduced in the 1980s as a method of manager training at AT&T, which proved that management coaching can help organizations improve performance and develop managers and leaders. In 2001, Gloeman published in the Harvard Business Review an article titled "Effective Leadership" which introduced coaching leadership. Leadership and management follow this style and behavior. Coaches help employees improve their performance and learning abilities by providing a management practice called coaching leadership. Coaches have shown effective leadership by providing feedback on employee performance, a sense of tolerance for uncertainty, working together as a cohesive team, etc. (Ellinger et.al. 1999), according to later research, coaching is defined as a manager's ability to demonstrate management effectiveness through feedback on employee performance (McLean, 2005). Even though there is some disagreement about the definition of leadership coaching, there is consensus on the identity of the constituent elements: leaders of these teams will be communicating effectively with their employees, focusing on teamwork, and focusing on individual learning

and development while accepting the environment. There are some distinctions between coaching and other types of positive leadership, such as inclusive leadership and servant leadership. Interactions emphasize motivation and inspiration for employees. Communication and positive interaction can lead to common development. A growing body of research indicates that coaching a leader's work behaviors has a positive impact on learning behavior, performance (Agarwal et.al, 2009), organizational commitment, professional commitment, work safety, and employee self-efficacy (Pousa,2015).

As defined by the definition of coaching, a manager serves as a coach to demonstrate their management effectiveness through feedback on employee performance, tolerance to uncertainty, emphasis on learning and cooperation, and so on. There are three levels of coaching factors influencing innovative behavior: the individual, the group, and the company (Anderson et.al. 2014), including the innovation requirements perceived, team environment, and human resource management practices. In studies, improving and breaking down the mental model of a person leads to a greater degree of innovation behavior. Coaches who emphasise employee inspiration and guide employees to solve problems independently will improve the mental model, which promotes innovative behavior. Leadership support will also enable the open and interactive environment in the organization to provide more resources and support for employees to practice innovative ideas, and further promote innovation behavior within the organization.

Motivating individuals to engage in specific behaviors. Motivation at work influences individuals to perform a series of behaviors related to job performance and determines the form, duration, and intensity of these behaviors. Motivation research can be traced back to Vroom's expectancy valence theory in 1964. Porter and Lawler later proposed a traditional motivation model, which separated motivations into intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. According to a large number of studies, motivation can effectively predict an employee's job performance, learning behavior, job adaptability, and job satisfaction.

Employers are now paying more attention to employee motivation in order to increase organizational performance through better employee incentives.

Deci and Ryan proposed the Self-determination Theory as a motivation theory. This theory is based on traditional theories of motivation. This theory has a wide range of application and is widely recognized. According to SDT, motivation is a continuum consisting of external regulation, introjection, integration, identification, and intrinsic motivation. "Internalization" of motivation is the process of moving from external regulation to intrinsic motivation, that is the level of acceptance of behavioral norms and the recognition of values of individuals [9]. Research has shown that the main influencing factors of motivation include the characteristics of the task itself, interest needs and emotional factors, goal setting, motivation, and feedback.

Leaders who coach employees emphasize encouragement and support so they discover and solve problems on their own. In addition, they decentralize their power and place importance on the training and professional development of employees, so they can get more opportunities at work. Coaching leaders will also enhance the level of work skill of employees. On the one hand, employees are able to satisfy their psychological needs for relatedness, competence, and autonomy, as well as demonstrating strong interest and confidence in the activities, promoting creativity and vitality [10]. Study results indicate that the ability of individual cognition to achieve its highest level is driven by motivation, identification and analysis of states can be more comprehensive, and more ideas can be proposed. There will be a greater passion among employees to promote innovation and participate in innovation activities.

3. Methodology

Following methodology was designed for the study to collect primary data.

- a. A sample of 120 respondents was selected for the purpose of the study using convenience sampling. The respondents were chose from 5 leading KPO organizations in Pune City.

- b. Design and validate a (minimum 10-point) questionnaire for ascertainment of
 - i. Employee Innovation
 - ii. Leadership Coaching
 - iii. Employee motivation
- c. Seek responses on a 5-point Likert scale
- d. Conduct the survey
- e. Summarize the responses
- f. Apply correlation analysis.
- g. Analyse the results

- ii. Leadership Coaching (10 items)
- iii. Level of Employee motivation (10 items)
- b. For each of the sections an average/ scores were calculated.
- c. Percentages to questions under a particular section of the questionnaire were averaged to get a single score for that section,
- d. P-values were calculated, and the null hypotheses was checked for rejection or non-rejection.

The study was conducted across Pune City.

Scheme formed for testing of hypotheses

- a. Responses were collected under 4 sections:
 - 1. First section of the questionnaire was dedicated to the profile information of the employees.
 - 2. The second, third and fourth sections were dedicated to measure the following variables:
 - i. Level of Employee Innovation (10 items)

Cronbach’s alpha score for the questionnaire was calculated the results have been discussed in the next section of the paper. The hypotheses set in this regard were as under:

Hypothesis:

H1o: There is no correlation between Level of leadership coaching, Work motivation and employee innovation
 H1a: Level of leadership coaching and Work motivation have significant positive correlations with employee innovation.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Results of the Cronbach’s Alpha

Sr. No.	Section of the questionnaire	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha value
1	Level of Employee Innovation	10	0.823
2	Level of Leadership Coaching	10	0.813
3	Level of Employee motivation	10	0.834
4	Complete Questionnaire	30	0.784

The above table shows that the values of Cronbach’s alpha were above 0.7 in each of the cases. This shows the level of internal

consistency and proves the validity of the measures that have been calculated.

Table 2: Correlations

Correlations				
		Employee Innovation	Leadership Coaching	Employee motivation
Employee Innovation	Pearson Correlation	1	.542**	.573**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	120	120	120
Leadership Coaching	Pearson Correlation	.542**	1	.471**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	120	120	120
Employee motivation	Pearson Correlation	.573**	.471**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In each of the cases above, every variable has a significant positive correlation with other variables ($p < 0.01$). Therefore, Level of leadership coaching and Work motivation have significant positive correlations with employee innovation.

5. Conclusion

While coaching leadership is a novel form of leadership in the area of organisational behaviour, it attempts to develop workers' brains, the academic community has not examined the intermediate mechanism that connects the two. The majority of research on coaching leadership focuses on its primary impacts, while the majority of research on intermediates focuses on psychological capital. The primary psychological aspect affecting an individual's conduct is their motivation.

Leadership coaching, the research found, has a considerable effect on creative behaviour. The research revealed that job motivation may play a unique mediating function in the coaching innovation process. This contributes to the enrichment of society's attitude to coaching and innovative behaviour. Employees will also be able to satisfy their own psychological needs

and develop a feeling of self-determination as a result of coaching leadership's active supervision, fostering collaboration, and concentrating on communication and other behaviours. Employees demonstrated increased enthusiasm for their job, a greater willingness to engage in collaboration and missions, and a greater willingness to actively research challenges and support innovation.

This research has a lot of flaws and limitations. There are certain limits to the accuracy and impartiality of self-assessment methods used to evaluate data from the same data source. Future study may explore leader-employee pairing survey approaches to gather data and increase the accuracy of outcomes. Second, this research focuses only on the mediating effect of job motivation. Additional theoretical viewpoints on the subject may supplement this work. Finally, this research makes no mention of the importance of individual personality factors in the influence process, such as personal values and regulatory orientation. In the future, researchers may examine exploring the boundary conditions associated with the process of coaching leadership and creativity.

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